

Applications of Natural Dye Extracted from Malabar spinach and Red spinach as Photosensitizers in Dye-Sensitized Solar Cell

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ABSTRACT

Dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) have emerged as an innovative solar energy conversion technology that offers a new path for sustainable power generation. Typical DSSC consists of a sensitizing dye chemically bound to a nanocrystalline semiconductor oxide. In this study, two natural dyes were extracted from Malabar spinach and red spinach respectively, and used as photosensitizers to construct the DSSCs. The candle nip carbon coating technique was employed to prepare the counter electrodes, and a redox liquid iodine (I^-/I_3^-) was used as an electrolyte. UV-vis spectroscopy was utilized to investigate the absorption range of the extracted dyes, while FT-IR was utilized to analyze the functional groups present. The photovoltaic properties of the cells, as well as their efficiency, were evaluated using current-voltage (I-V) curves. The extracted dyes showed significant optical absorption in ultraviolet and visible regions. The FT-IR spectra confirmed the presence of anchoring groups in the dye solutions. DSSC based on Malabar spinach dye has shown an open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of 0.64 V, a short-circuit current (I_{sc}) of 0.49 mA, a fill factor (FF) of 0.52, and a photoelectric conversion efficiency of 0.16%. In contrast, DSSC based on red spinach extract shows a photoelectric conversion efficiency of 0.14% with an open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of 0.61 V, a short circuit current (I_{sc}) of 0.41 mA, and a fill factor (FF) of 0.43.

1. INTRODUCTION

The world's energy consumption is increasing day by day due to rapid population growth and the massive industrial revolution [1]. To mitigate excessive energy consumption photovoltaic (PV)

solar cell devices can play a vital role. Dye sensitized solar cell (DSSC) is a third-generation solar cell that utilizes photoelectrochemical processes to harness solar radiation. The concept of DSSC was first introduced by O'Regan and

Gratzel in 1991 [2]. DSSC offers some advantages over conventional silicon-based solar cells including a simple manufacturing process, minimum cost, environment friendly, and good performance under slightly low light conditions. It was found that the first developed DSSC absorbs visible light up to about 800 nm and the photo conversion efficiency (PCE) is over 7%. Researchers from EPFL groups of Grätzel and Anders Hagfeldt have now developed a way to improve the packing of two newly designed photosensitizer dye molecules to enhance the PCE of DSSC. The team was able to show DSSCs with a PCE of 15.2% under standard global simulated sunlight after testing its long-term operational stability over 500 hours by this method. The power conversion efficiency was between 28.4% and 30.2% over a broad range of ambient light intensities with exceptional stability by extending the active surface area of the electrode where metal complex organic dye molecules were used as photosensitizers [3].

DSSCs are categorized as photoelectrochemical solar cells instead of solid-state p-n junction solar cells since they contain redox electrolytes and natural dye. Recently, research has focused on readily available dyes derived from natural sources as photosensitizers because of their large absorption coefficients, high light-harvesting efficiency, low cost, ease of production, and environmental friendliness [4]. Natural dyes are easy to extract from natural resources such as flowers, leaves, fruit, tree bark, stems, and seeds. The most commonly used natural organic pigments are chlorophyll, anthocyanins, carotenes, betacyanins, and curcumin. DSSC sensitized with natural pigments containing anthocyanins and chlorophylls has demonstrated an overall PCE of less than 1% [5].

Typically, DSSC consists of four main parts as shown in figure 1: (1) transparent conductive oxide glass (Fluorine-doped tin oxide or Indium doped tin oxide substrate) (2) nano-crystalline semiconductor (ZnO , TiO_2 , SnO_2) (3) redox iodide electrolyte (4) cathode (conducting glass coated with graphite or platinum) [6]. In DSSCs, when light falls on the photoanode the dye molecules absorb photons and become excited. An excited dye molecule injects an electron into the

conduction band of mesoporous TiO_2 and as a result, dye molecules get oxidized. These injected electrons travel through the TiO_2 layer to the external circuit to reach the counter electrode (cathode). These electrons are then transferred to the electrolyte where the oxidized dye accepts electrons from the iodide ion to replace the lost electron and at the same time, the iodide molecules are oxidized to triiodide and the regeneration process continuously takes place.

Thus, the cell operation is based on consecutive oxidation/reduction cycles and, an ideal cell converts solar energy into electricity without any net consumption of chemicals, thus the DSSC can continuously supply power. DSSC offers some advantages including low cost, mechanical robustness, the ability to work in low-light conditions, pollution-free, and easy to handle.

Fig. 1: Schematic representation of DSSC

In this work, natural dyes were extracted from Red spinach (*Amaranthus dubius*) and Malabar spinach (*Basella alba*) and used as photosensitizers for the DSSCs. Malabar spinach and Red spinach are two plants abundant in nature and have rich pigment content. These natural dyes, structurally consisting of complex organic molecules such as Chlorophylls and anthocyanins show excellent light-absorbing properties that make them good candidates for sensitizing DSSCs [7]. The optical characteristics of the extracted dyes of Malabar spinach and Red spinach were studied by using UV-Vis absorption, and FT-IR spectroscopy techniques. Finally, the photoconversion efficiency of fabricated DSSCs were studied.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Chemicals

Titanium dioxide nano-powder (TiO_2 , 99.5%, 21nm) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Polyethylene glycol (PEG, Mw =1000), Triton X-100, Potassium Iodide (KI), Iodine (I_2), and Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) were purchased from Research-Lab Fine Chem Industries (India).

2.2 Extraction of natural dye photosensitizer

Natural green and red dyes were extracted from Malabar spinach and red spinach, respectively as shown in Figure 2. These species were collected from the local agricultural farm (Dhaka, Bangladesh).

Fig. 2: Extraction of natural dye from Malabar spinach and Red spinach

Malabar spinach leaves were washed and dried at 30°C in a vacuum drying oven for 1 hour to remove moisture to prepare the ethanol extract of dye. Then the leaves were cut into small pieces and meshed with mortar and pestle. In the next step, 20g Malabar spinach sliced leaves were kept in 10 ml 99.9 wt.% ethanol solution and wrapped by aluminum foil paper for 24 hours without exposure to sunlight. Finally, solid residues were filtered out and used as a sensitizer supply for DSSC. The green dye extract was stored in a glass bottle, wrapped in aluminum foil to prevent exposure to external light, and stored in a refrigerator away from light and oxygen to ensure dye stability.

Natural red dye extracted from leaves of Red spinach in deionized (DI) water. Firstly, the red spinach plant leaves were washed with DI water and cut into pieces. Then, the sliced leaves were immersed in DI water (10g:1 ml volume ratio) and heated at 60°C for 45 minutes. The liquid solution was cooled down and solid residues were filtered out and used as a dye sensitizer source for DSSC. The red dye extract was stored in an amber glass bottle and refrigerator in the absence of light and oxygen.

2.3 Preparation of TiO_2 Paste

To the preparation of TiO_2 paste 1 ml of ethanol, 2 ml of Triton-X, and 0.2 ml of Polyethylene glycol were poured into a mortar that contained 1 gram of titanium (IV) oxide. By using a pestle the mixture was mixed homogeneously for 30 minutes at room temperature, thus titanium dioxide paste was prepared.

2.4 Preparation of Photoanode

For photoanode fabrication, FTO glass substrates were cleaned in an ultrasonic bath with detergent, deionized water, ethanol, and acetone solution (50:50 ratio) to remove any organic or inorganic contaminants or adhesives on their surface. Each step was performed for 10 minutes. TiO_2 paste was applied onto the conductive side of the FTO glass substrate for the transparent TiO_2 anode. The area of the active cell was $1.5 \times 1.5 \text{ cm}^2$. The single-layer nanoporous TiO_2 film was air-dried and sintered at 450°C in a muffle furnace for 1 hour and allowed to cool for 12 hours.

2.5 Preparation of Electrolyte

The iodine electrolyte solution was prepared by previously reported [8] as making a homogeneous mixture by stirring 0.83 g potassium iodide (KI), 0.127 g iodine (I_2), and 10 ml polyethylene glycol in a beaker by using a magnetic stirrer for 10 minutes. Then the prepared liquid iodine electrolyte solution was stored in a dark container out of direct sunlight.

2.6 Dye loading

The anode was dipped into 25 ml of dye solution for 60 min to fabricate a working photoanode. All of the two extracted dyes were used as sensitizers for DSSC. Dye pigments were adsorbed by the mesoporous layer of TiO₂ photoanode and the photoanodes were cleaned with DI water for 5-8 s to remove (if any) unbound dye pigments. The photoanode was then dried in an air drier at 40°C for 1 hour. The average dye absorbed by Photoanode was about 9–10% of the initial concentration.

Fig. 3: Total fabrication procedure of DSSC (a) Cutting and cleaning of FTO glass, (b) resistivity checked by multimeter, (c) application of TiO₂ paste by doctor blade technique (d) annealed anode (e) dipping anode into dye solution (f) adsorption of dye into the anode, (g) + (h) preparation of cathode (i) preparation of electrolyte (j) fabrication of DSSC.

2.7 Device fabrication

The cathode was prepared by covering the clean FTO (in the Anode Preparation section) glass by candle nip carbon coating technique on the conductive side of the glass substrate. The photoanode and cathode were fabricated in a sandwich-type cell and a liquid electrolytic solution (Electrolyte preparation in section) was injected into the cell as shown in Figure 3.

2.8 Characterization and Measurements

The absorption spectra of extracted natural dyes were performed using a T- 60 UV-visible spectrometer (PG Electronics, UK). UV-visible spectroscopy is a method of determining which wavelength (colors) of visible light, a sample absorbs or emits. To confirm the structure, functional group, and chemical bond of the dye samples, we used a PerkinElmer Spectrum Two FTIR spectrophotometer, UK in region 400 to 4000 cm⁻¹ with suitable scan resolutions. The photovoltaic response of fabricated DSSC was measured by illumination under 100mW/cm² radiation from a solar simulator. The FF (Fill factor) of DSSC can be measured from the photo current-voltage (I-V) curve by using the following formula [9]:

$$FF = \frac{I_{max} \times V_{max}}{I_{sc} \times V_{oc}} \quad (1)$$

Where, I_{max} and V_{max} are the current and voltage of maximum power output respectively; I_{sc} is the short-circuit current and V_{oc} is the open-circuit voltage. The overall photoconversion efficiency of a solar cell is defined as the ratio of the maximum output of the cell divided by the power of the incident light. The photoconversion efficiency of the DSSC has been determined by using the following formula [9]:

$$\eta = \frac{I_{sc} \times V_{oc} \times FF}{P_{in}} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

where P_{in} is the input power.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Absorption spectra of extracted dyes

Leaves of two plants were selected for dye extraction because it was thought that they have certain compounds i.e. chlorophyll, anthocyanin, or betaxanthin which are responsible for generating electrons upon absorption of photons and injecting them into the conduction band of the photoanode material via functional groups which serve as anchoring groups to the photoanode [10]. A requirement for a dye to qualify as a sensitizer is to have optical absorption in UV and/or visible regions. The presence of these compounds or their lack of it in the extracted dyes was studied via UV-vis spectroscopy. Fig 4–5, shows the absorption

spectra of Malabar spinach, and Red spinach dye respectively.

The absorption spectra of Malabar spinach and red spinach dye extract are shown in Fig. 3 and Figure 4, respectively. The presence of peaks from 400 nm to 700 nm (i.e. the visible light spectrum) confirms that the dye extraction process was successful. According to the absorption spectrum of chlorophyll a, two absorption regions are found in the wavelength ranges of 380-480 nm and 560-680 nm [11]. Some absorption peaks are visible at 400 nm to 700 nm, where the peaks at 435 and 665 nm correlate with chlorophyll a. The peaks at 470 nm were influenced by chlorophyll b [12].

The average spectra show Malabar spinach has higher chlorophyll absorption than red spinach in all peaks. Based on [13], the higher the chlorophyll content, the higher the absorption value and the higher the number of molecules that can absorb photons. The low absorption of the sample around 500 nm indicates the transmission (or reflection) of green light in the visible light spectrum by the green dye (chlorophyll). The peaks show that the dye is sensitive to both UV and visible light. Therefore, it showed promising prospects for use as a dye in cell manufacturing. The DSSC efficiency value also depends on the absorbance of the wavelength used. The broader the absorption spectrum of the chlorophyll dye, the more light frequencies can be absorbed by the dye sensitized solar cell [14].

Fig. 4: Absorption spectrum of Malabar spinach dye

Fig. 5: Absorption spectrum of Red spinach dye extract

3.2 Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) Spectra of extracted natural dyes

The FTIR absorbance spectra were measured by an FTIR 7800 spectrometer for the chemical characterization of the extracted natural dyes which are illustrated in Figure 6 and Figure 7, while Table 1 lists the characteristics of IR frequencies of organic functional groups of extracted natural dye molecules. In DSSC, dyes must have some specific functional group for effective absorption onto TiO_2 thin film [15]. The functional group and chemical bonds present in Malabar spinach and Red spinach dye extract were investigated through FTIR characterization.

Fig. 6: FTIR spectrum of Malabar spinach dye extract

The FTIR spectrum of Malabar spinach dye extract shows a broad and strong peak at 3306 cm^{-1} due to the presence of the O-H functional group [16]. The peak at 2952 cm^{-1} is attributed to

the C-H stretching vibration of alkane. The peaks at 1645 cm^{-1} and 1409 cm^{-1} correspond to C=C stretching vibrations confirming the presence of an aromatic ring structure. Another absorption peak at 1012 cm^{-1} corresponds to asymmetric C-O stretching vibration. The FTIR spectrum of Red spinach dye extract shows a broad and strong peak at 3298 cm^{-1} attributed to the O-H stretching vibration. The absorption peak at 1636 cm^{-1} band is associated with C=C stretching. Furthermore, a peak at 601 cm^{-1} is assigned to C-Cl stretching vibration.

Fig. 7: FTIR spectrum of Red spinach dye extract

Table 1: IR absorption of organic functional groups of extracted natural dyes

Functional group	Absorption range	Types of vibration	Intensity	Absorption peak of Malabar spinach dye	Absorption peak of Red spinach dye	Ref.
Alcohol (O-H)	3200–3600	Stretch (asymmetric)	Strong	3306	3298	[17]
Alkane (C-H)	2850–3000	Stretch (symmetric)	Weak	2952	-	[18]
Alkane (C-H)	2820–2850	Stretch	Weak	2844	-	[19]
Alkene (C=C)	1620–1680	Stretch	Variable	1645	1636	[20]
Aromatic (C=C)	1400–1600	Stretch	Weak	1409	-	[21]
Ether (C-O)	1000–1300	Stretch	Strong	1012	-	[22, 23]

Alkyl Halide (C-Cl)	600–800	Stretch	Strong	624	601	[24]
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3.3 Photoelectric properties of DSSC

The efficiency of fabricated DSSC has been calculated by using the current-voltage (I-V) characteristics curve. The I-V performance of the assembled cells was measured under a calibrated solar simulator with a 500 W Xenon arc lamp and a light intensity of 100 mW/cm^2 shown in Figure 8. From the I-V characteristic curve short circuit current (I_{sc}), Open circuit voltage (V_{oc}), and fill factor (FF) were calculated. The fill factor (FF) and photoconversion efficiency (η) of fabricated DSSCs were calculated by using equations 1 and 2 respectively. The photoelectrical parameters of fabricated DSSCs such as I_{sc} , V_{oc} , FF, and η values are given in Table 2. At normal room (or lab) conditions, all the cell parameters were measured.

Fig. 8: I-V characteristics curve of DSSC based on extracted natural dyes

Table 2: Photo-electrochemical parameters for DSSCs sensitized by Malabar spinach and Red spinach dye with TiO_2 as photoanode

Natural Dye	I_{sc} (mA)	I_{max} (mA)	V_{oc} (V)	V_{max} (V)	FF	Efficiency, η (%)
Malabar spinach	0.49	0.32	0.64	0.51	0.52	0.16
Red spinach	0.41	0.28	0.61	0.49	0.43	0.14

According to Table 2, Malabar spinach dye-based DSSC has shown better cell parameters ($I_{sc} = 0.49$ mA, $V_{oc} = 0.64$ V, $FF = 0.52$ and $\eta = 0.16\%$) compared to Red spinach dye-based DSSC's cell parameter ($I_{sc} = 0.41$ mA, $V_{oc} = 0.61$ V, $FF = 0.43$ and $\eta = 0.14\%$).

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, DSSC has been successfully fabricated by using natural dye extracted from Malabar spinach and Red spinach respectively. The UV-vis absorption spectroscopy studies confirm the dye extract has shown absorption in the visible regions at 400-700nm. From the FTIR spectroscopy analysis, it was confirmed that the functional groups of interest were present in extracted natural dyes. The maximum current was observed for DSSC based on Malabar spinach (0.49 mA), whereas DSSC showed the minimum based on Red spinach (0.41 mA). The highest photoconversion efficiency of 0.16% was exhibited by Malabar spinach dye based DSSC, while a quite low photoconversion efficiency of 0.14% was shown by Red spinach dye based DSSC. It was found that DSSC prepared with Malabar spinach dye is more efficient than that prepared with Red spinach dye.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors have confirmed that there is no conflict of interest with this work.

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